

PRESERVE

INNOVATION ROADMAP 2030

About us

High Performance Sustainable Bio-based Packaging with Tailored End of Life and Upcycled Secondary Use

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Executive Summary

The PRESERVE project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, aims to advance packaging sustainability by developing bio-based materials and innovative recycling solutions. Running from January 2021 to December 2024, the project sought to address critical challenges in the packaging industry, including the dependence on fossil-based plastics, inefficiencies in recycling systems, and the environmental impact of packaging waste.

Over its four-year duration, PRESERVE focused on creating bio-based alternatives to traditional packaging materials. These innovations incorporated advanced methodologies to improve recyclability, enable biodegradation as an end-of-life option, and facilitate upcycling. The project also introduced technologies like protein-based coatings and enzymatic treatments to reduce microplastic release and enhance the circularity of materials. To support these efforts, PRESERVE developed tools such as a Decision Support System, enabling data-driven decision-making for material selection and lifecycle optimisation.

The project engaged 23 partners across ten countries, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration along the value chain to ensure solutions were practical, scalable, and aligned with market and regulatory requirements. While PRESERVE achieved significant milestones in eco-design and recycling processes, challenges remain in scaling up these innovations and addressing cost barriers to market entry.

As PRESERVE concludes, its findings underscore the need for continued investment in sustainable packaging technologies and more substantial alignment between policy and industrial practices. The project provides a foundation for future initiatives to transform the packaging sector toward a circular and environmentally responsible model.

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PRESERVE in a nutshell

PRESERVE is a European research project committed to developing bio-based packaging and funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

We are the pioneers in sustainability.

The 4-year project started in January 2021 and has finished its activities in December 2024. The project focuses on approaches tailored to improve the recyclability of multi-materials, biodegradation as an end-of-life option, versatility and upcycled secondary application, and the use of novel methodologies to reduce the release of microplastics based on the application of functional finishing treatments.

The consortium is formed by 23 partners from 10 countries. It covers the whole supply and value chain. It brings together comprehensive interdisciplinary pockets of knowledge, assessing the performance of developed solutions and upscaling them to introduce new viable circular bio-based packaging solutions into the market.

PRESERVE's upcycling strategies to boost packaging performance in the first and subsequent life cycles of the materials comprise several steps:

- Better packaging design allowing delamination with bio-based barrier coatings and adhesives, eBeam treatment and enzymation to prevent microplastic release.
- Establishment of a delamination pilot plant, with subsequent adjusting and upscaling of the new recycling process, with an initial sorting via advanced photonic and artificial intelligence approaches.
- Development of upcycled demonstrators deriving from recycled food packaging, with at least 85% of recovered materials for non-food-contact applications.

OUR VISION

In Europe, plastic packaging continues to see high demand but with varying recycling success. In 2022, the EU generated approximately 83.4 million tonnes of total packaging waste, with plastic packaging accounting for about 36.1 kg per person. Of this, an estimated 41% of plastic packaging waste was recycled, an improvement from 38% a decade ago. However, despite advances, this rate lags behind materials like glass and steel, which boast recycling rates of over 80%. Given these numbers, improving the circularity of plastic packaging from origin to subsequent life cycles is more than urgent.

Our vision is to contribute to the transition towards a sustainable and circular economy by innovating bio-based or recycled materials for packaging applications that reduce environmental impact, enhance resource efficiency, and support economic growth. Introducing a life cycle approach with innovative materials can help us reach unexplored new potential for plastic packaging and its end-of-life. In PRESERVE, we have the potential to change up to 60% of packaging currently used by the market.

The benefits deriving from new approaches and uses of bioplastics, adhesives and biopolymers can help us upcycle materials used and create secondary raw materials to create new products, thus reducing the waste generated and the impact on landfill waste.

At PRESERVE, we established an ambitious interdisciplinary plan based on refined strategies and methodologies, with key defined objectives and milestones, to accomplish our vision. All these elements have formed our mission for the past four years and led to a list of innovation breakthroughs presented in this Roadmap.

THE PRESERVE MISSION

The Change we want to achieve

The main focus of the PRESERVE project has been to substitute fossil fuels-derived plastics used in food and drink packaging with biobased ones thanks to the improvement of their properties.

The PRESERVE project has made significant strides toward reducing reliance on fossil-based plastics in packaging, but specific challenges remain in achieving full-scale market readiness. Throughout the project, we developed advanced biobased materials and tested novel recycling and upcycling processes, yielding valuable insights into resource conservation, lifecycle performance, and environmental impact reduction. While these solutions may require further refinement to meet economic and scalability benchmarks, the groundwork laid by PRESERVE marks a key step forward in the journey to sustainable packaging.

Our eco-designed biobased solutions – created from primary and secondary renewable raw materials – demonstrated the potential to reduce the direct and indirect release of plastics and microplastics. These results highlight the importance of ongoing innovation, particularly in refining material performance and enhancing integration within existing packaging systems.

As we conclude, the PRESERVE project has equipped the industry with practical data, refined processes, and a clear understanding of future challenges. This work provides a valuable foundation for next-generation efforts to realise a circular economy for biobased packaging materials and underscores the critical steps needed for a sustainable transition.

Driving Change Through Strategy and Sustainability

The PRESERVE project has employed a holistic approach to drive meaningful change in the packaging sector. By integrating **exploitation, dissemination, policy engagement, innovation management, and comprehensive sustainability assessments**, we have ensured that the biobased packaging solutions developed are innovative, safe, environmentally sound, and economically viable.

- **Innovation Management**

Innovation management was critical in driving our biobased packaging solutions' successful development and eventual market readiness. An innovation management strategy must ensure research outcomes are systematically aligned with market demands and customer needs while maximising their impact. This approach bridges the gap between scientific research and practical applications, driving the successful development and adoption of biobased packaging solutions.

Within the PRESERVE project, we have used different tools to map the innovation and developed a tailored Innovation Notification System Register (INSR). The INSR has provided a structured mechanism to identify and manage innovations within the project.

The INSR is built on four essential tools that provide a structured approach to innovation management: Key Exploitable Results (KER) forms, KPI reference tables, Demonstrator forms, and Technology Readiness Level (TRL) advance tables.

Together, these tools facilitated the identification of market opportunities, clarified value propositions required by specific customer segments, and tracked the progress of innovations toward commercialisation. With the INSR, innovation was managed and maximised, ensuring sustainable solutions with meaningful impact.

- **Exploitation**

The exploitation of PRESERVE's results has been a key driver of the project's impact. The exploitation strategy of a European project lies in ensuring that the project's results are effectively utilised to generate economic, social, or environmental impact while aligning with the European Union's (EU) overarching goals. This approach addresses translating research outputs into actionable solutions that contribute to policy objectives, societal challenges, and market opportunities. The exploitation of PRESERVE's results has been a key driver of the project's impact.

A strong exploitation strategy identifies market opportunities and stakeholder needs early in the project. For each project result, it is essential to assess their status from lab to market, while engagement with end-users ensures that the solutions are practical and applicable. This also involves considering intellectual property rights (IPR) management for European projects to protect and promote results effectively. This market-oriented approach maximises the project's return on investment and enhances its relevance to industry and society.

Beyond market potential, exploitation strategies in European projects are designed to support EU policy goals and reinforce the European Research Area (ERA). This involves ensuring that results are aligned with EU directives and regulations. Disseminating outcomes to policymakers, regional authorities, and civil society further strengthens their impact, fostering innovation ecosystems that support long-term sustainability and collaboration.

By adopting an exploitation strategy, PRESERVE ensured its results were innovative and impactful, addressing societal needs and fostering economic growth while contributing to the EU's global leadership in research and innovation.

• Dissemination

The main aim of the PRESERVE dissemination strategy has been sharing the project results with the identified stakeholders – also referred to as target audiences – that may use the results through an array of activities from the moment project results have been available. The dissemination activities implemented during the project intend to reach the following four general objectives:

1. To share scientific research knowledge and innovation findings in the key sectors addressed by the project.
2. To disseminate methodologies and processes identified to improve the research capacity in the key sectors addressed by the project.
3. To reach cooperation activities with the most relevant key identified stakeholders.
4. To facilitate knowledge transfer and support upscaling of the results obtained by the RTDs with a view to seamless post-project replication.

• Safety, Environmental and Economic Sustainability

An environmental Life Cycle Assessment (e-LCA), a Life Cycle Costing analysis (LCC), and a Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA) have been performed on the obtained materials to provide recommendations for eco-designing the final products. The sustainability of these products will also be assessed. A Decision Support System (DSS) has been developed to support decisions at the packaging designer, recycler, and end-user levels.

Sustainability is most often defined as meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. A company implements sustainable practices by reducing its consumption of limited resources or finding alternative resources with lower environmental consequences.

Sustainability has three main pillars: economic, environmental, and social. **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** has been used as a methodology to evaluate the environmental impact of the circular use of bio-based packaging in PRESERVE by ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 guidelines. LCA results will help the decision-makers characterise the environmental trade-offs associated with product or process alternatives and select less aggressive ones for the environment.

Life Cycle Costing (LCC) has been used as an analytical methodology to measure direct and indirect cost variations resulting from applying the proposed technologies for each product life cycle stage. The LCC results will contribute to the development of business plans and will push the introduction of biobased packaging to the market.

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) has been used as a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, taking into account the consumer perception of sustainable market choices. It can be applied on its own or combined with other techniques.

A circular economy requires the eco-design of the products to reduce waste to a minimum and extend the product life cycle. This can be analysed through LCA, but a circularity assessment can also help analyse the sustainability outcomes. **Circularity** and LCA assessments are techniques used to assess environmental performance using complementary methodologies.

The Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation for carrying out circularity analysis is the most well-known methodology. This MCI allows us to measure to what extent the product has minimised the linear flow and restorative flow has been maximised.

The calculation of the circularity indicator, along with LCA results at the design stage, can lead to an eco-design as it allows companies to focus on the hotspots of their products that can increase their sustainability.

THE PRESERVE INNOVATION

The PRESERVE project has pursued a comprehensive approach to achieving impactful, sustainable change by leveraging exploitation, dissemination, policy engagement, and structured innovation management. These elements have been essential in guiding the project from concept to impactful outcomes, fostering an environment that supports immediate advancements and long-term sustainability goals.

Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) are a type of measurement system used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology. Each technology project is evaluated against the parameters for each technology level and is then assigned a TRL rating based on the projects progress. There are nine technology readiness levels. TRL 1 is the lowest and TRL 9 is the highest.

Technology readiness levels (TRL). Source, Horizon 2020 Work Programme.

1.The PRESERVE Technology and research

This section presents the PRESERVE results, with a brief description of the result, a description of the innovation breakthrough represented by this result, and a description of the strategic action needed to bring this innovation to market. Every result is accompanied by the TRL achieved at the start and finish. Our results are divided into coatings, end-of-life, and upcycling.

1

100% solid PHA coating formulations to improve the water resistance and water-vapour barrier properties of bio-based food and drink packaging

2

Coating formulation to improve or prevent microfiber release on textile and improved tests regarding efficiency

3

Metallisation on protein coatings for improved oxygen barrier

4

Method for multilayers separation in recycling plants

5

Method for the production of fibrillar or self-reinforced biopolymers

6

ECO-design of packaging materials and SRM applications

7

New upcycling methods, systems and/or technologies including new composite recipe and applications

This section presents the PRESERVE results, with a brief description of the result, a description of the innovation breakthrough represented by this result, and a description of the strategic action needed to bring this innovation to market. Every result is accompanied by the starting and finishing TRL achieved. Our results are divided into three categories: coatings, end-of-life, and upcycling.

Coatings

1. 100% solid PHA coating formulations to improve the water resistance and water-vapour barrier properties of bio-based food and drink packaging

- **Description of result**

Currently, traditional coatings are made with fossil fuel-based polyethylene or other solutions such as PLA, acrylic or wax coatings, which hinders the recyclability of the products.

- **Innovation breakthrough**

The PHA coatings developed in this project will serve as a sustainable alternative to the coatings that currently cover most paper and board products since they will be home-compostable and facilitate reducing the consumption of polymers from fossil sources.

TRL 3-4

TRL 5-6

- **Strategic actions to market**

This result has been protected with a patent. Several key aspects need to be addressed to progress from TRL 6 to TRL 9. The primary challenge is to lower the cost of the final price of the product, which at the moment is higher than that of existing materials. To address these challenges, imperfections in the formulation must be corrected. This includes finalising the composition of the material and achieving the desired thickness for optimal performance. The timeline for developing a fully functioning prototype is estimated to be between two and four years, depending on the formulation optimisation and testing speed. This period will require a consistent effort to resolve technical uncertainties and refine the product to meet market and operational demands.

2. Coating formulation to improve or prevent microfiber release on textile and improved tests regarding efficiency

- **Description of result**

Currently, no commercial finishes on the market reduce the microfibre release of textiles. The textile industry suffers from issues regarding microfibre shedding during the use phase and washing. The result consists of a formulation which reduces the number of microfibers released from an (r-)PET or (r-)PLA fabric and is not harmful to organisms in the environment.

- **Innovation breakthrough**

The developed product is new on the market and anticipates current issues in the textile sector regarding microfibre release.

TRL 5

TRL 6

- **Strategic actions to market**

Several steps are necessary to commercialise the innovative formulation designed to reduce microfibre release successfully. Industrial scale-up faces challenges such as ensuring consistent performance across different textile applications and validating its safety and efficacy at larger scales. Imperfections to address include optimising the formulation for durability and compatibility with various textiles during the use and washing phases. Developing a fully functioning prototype could take 2-3 years, contingent on rigorous testing and refinement. Collaboration with end users in the textile industry will be critical to tailor the product to real-world needs. At the same time, partnerships with key market players can aid in scaling production and market entry.

3. Metallisation on protein coatings for improved oxygen barrier

- **Description of result**

Metallisation of packaging layers enhances barrier properties, resulting in an almost impermeable layer. The downside is that upon application on polymer films, it interferes with their recycling, resulting in colour distortion. Combining the protein coating and metallisation would simplify the delamination process and show ultra-high oxygen barrier properties.

- **Innovation breakthrough**

This innovation addresses a critical challenge in polymer recycling by ensuring that metallisation applied to a protein coating does not interfere with recycling processes. When the protein coating is enzymatically degraded for delamination, the metallisation ends up in the wash water. Consequently, the metallisation will not affect polymer recycling.

Metallising protein-based coatings usually bear the risk of damage occurring in the protein layer in the form of cracks and holes due to metallisation in the high vacuum chamber.

Despite previous concerns, no visible nor measurable defects in the WPI-layer on the substrate could be detected, and excellent barrier properties could be achieved. Investigated substrates were films of PLA, PET, and PE. For comparison purposes, all three substrates were first coated with protein and metallised in the next step. Barrier properties in the form of measurements for OTR and WVTR were used to track the improvement of each coating step compared to the uncoated substrate. Also, as an alternative option for facilitating the implementation of this solution, a higher TRL, metallised commercially available substrates were coated and tested, obtaining successful results in barrier properties.

TRL 3-4

TRL 5-6

- **Strategic actions to market**

Further steps include optimising the process for industrial conditions, securing consistent quality across diverse substrates, and conducting large-scale validation to ensure recyclability and barrier performance. The development of a final prototype is expected to take approximately three to four years, contingent upon the successful resolution of a significant challenge that has emerged during the project. This challenge pertains to the lamination of protein-coated and protein-coated films with additional metallisation. It is attributed, in part, to an inadequate degree of adhesion between the substrate film, the protein coating, and the metallisation, depending on the substrate type.

Therefore, collaboration with adhesive producers, packaging manufacturers and recyclers will be essential for integration into the value chain. At the same time, IP actions should focus on protecting the unique metallisation and delamination methods to strengthen the market position. Additionally, some investments must be made in mixing equipment to produce the coatings on-site, at the printing stage, since the conventional converting techniques don't include coating preparation and the WPI coating has a short shelf-life before drying. Hence, it needs to be prepared on the application site.

End of Life

4. Method for multilayers separation in recycling plants

- **Description of result**

Within PRESERVE, a new method for the elimination of bio-based coatings has been developed. Using an enzymatic soap, whey-based coating from PE, PET, cardboard, PLA, and multilayer has been removed. A complete delamination process has been developed in four steps: shredding, washing, separation, and pelletising.

- **Innovation breakthrough**

This method will facilitate the separation of multilayer packaging containing the PRESERVE protein coating, thereby enabling the recycling and recovery of biobased materials efficiently and straightforwardly. Furthermore, the method is readily replicable.

- **Strategic actions to market**

To move from TRL 6 to TRL 9, the delamination time of materials must be reduced from hours to the order of minutes to be integrated into post-consumer recycling processes. This can be achieved by developing optimised soap formulations and the chemistry used in washing processes. Moving from a batch system to a continuous system is also necessary to collect more data. Make investments to integrate the system into larger recycling systems and be able to process large volumes of materials. Work with recyclers, packaging manufacturers, and stakeholders interested in optimising the technology with existing processes and minimising investment costs. To carry out an economic and cost-benefit assessment of the introduction of the technology.

TRL 3-4

TRL 6

Upcycling

5. Method for the production of fibrillar or self-reinforced biopolymers

- **Description of result**

Numerous packaging materials are composed of several components to achieve the desired shelf-life properties. These co-extruded products, such as PA/PE or PET/PE films, often used for modified atmosphere packaging (MAP) or to provide puncture resistance of vacuum food packaging, are currently recycled as blends with inferior mechanical properties even after compatibilisation.

Processing polymer blends with a high draw ratio and forming a microfibrillar structure can be of significant interest because it can achieve a broad spectrum of properties without producing a new virgin polymer. It is possible to improve the mechanical and barrier properties using this technique. This strategy could also be applied to bio-based materials, which sometimes are at a disadvantage against fossil-based materials in terms of mechanical performance. But, this reinforcement allows them to be more competitive and reach new levels of efficiency.

- **Innovation breakthrough**

As mentioned, multilayer structures composed of different polymers, such as coextruded PET/PE films, are currently recycled into blends with reduced mechanical and barrier properties, considerably decreasing their chances of successfully adapting to an application. The challenge of this innovation is overcoming the reduction of properties with tailored strategies.

PRESERVE aims to produce bio-based microfibrillar reinforced PE/PET and PE/PA materials from recycling streams. As a result, intimate blending enables the creation of materials with customised properties that outperform existing homopolymers. Microfibrillar reinforcement is an interesting approach to upcycling mixed polymer waste with tailored applications. This strategy was also applied in mono-PLA cast films to improve their performance by thermoforming and stabilising the final packaging.

TRL 3-4

TRL 6

- **Strategic actions to market**

To advance this result from TRL 6 to TRL 9, efforts should focus on scaling the production of bio-based microfibrillar reinforced materials for packaging applications. Processing polymer blends with a high draw ratio to form a microfibrillar structure makes it possible to significantly enhance mechanical and barrier properties without developing new polymers.

This innovation has a high potential to be implemented on a higher TRL level. Therefore, a close collaboration between compounders, packaging producers, and recyclers (if the raw material is coming from a recycle stream) must take place to overcome minor challenges, like adjustments on the formulations to improve the processability of the blends or work on the adaptation of the moulds to the specific material. In general, this strategy will allow for the synergy between virgin bio-based materials and recycled materials, whether bio-based or not. It can be implemented in the next 1-2 years from a technical point of view.

6. ECO-design of packaging materials and SRM applications

- **Description of result**

Eco-design of packaging involves a concept where the materials used have less impact on the environment in each stage of the packaging life. This means bio-based raw materials, biodegradable (if possible) or recyclable Secondary Raw Materials (SRM) and less microplastic release. This method will offer more eco-friendly packaging solutions with a low environmental impact, less microplastic release, and an end-life closing the loop (SRM or biodegradable) independently from fossil-based raw materials.

- **Innovation breakthrough**

An application for these SRMs will also be found for the recyclable solutions. Packaging concepts and the use of SRM must usually be adapted. The pollution on the planet is increasing every day, and this eco-packaging concept will help reduce the CO2 footprint, reduce microplastic release, and encourage the reuse of resources. One of the risks related to this KER is the discontinuous availability of resources, quality of SRM and possible pollution/contamination in collected bio-based plastic. Paper pulp packaging and displays for marketing products made of fossil-based plastic.

- **Strategic actions to market**

To advance this eco-design packaging concept from TRL 6 to TRL 9, efforts must focus on optimising recyclable and biodegradable solutions while addressing challenges related to raw material sourcing and production scalability. This innovation reduces dependency on fossil-based materials and mitigates pollution by closing the material loop through secondary raw materials (SRM) or biodegradability. Recyclable solutions require adaptation of packaging designs and the practical application of SRMs, which must account for risks such as resource availability, SRM quality, and contamination in bio-based plastics.

TRL 3-4

TRL 6

The time to market is estimated at 1-2 years, encompassing final product design, engineering, material certification, and industrial-scale production. Investments will be needed for moulds, material sourcing, logistics, and organisational adjustments. Collaborations with material suppliers, certification bodies, and manufacturers will be key to ensuring scalability and market readiness.

Another vital collaboration needed for a successful market implementation is between the end-user (mainly from the cosmetic side) and the packaging producer to ensure the functionality of the packaging and the safety of the product since many cosmetics can interact with polymers, depending on their chemical resistance to any specific substances.

7. New upcycling methods, systems and/or technologies including new composite recipe and applications

- **Description of result**

In PRESERVE, we have developed a demonstrator that proves that industrial recycling of discarded bio-based plastic packaging (PLA) can lead to a new, attractive and reproducible non-food product application that may be of value to the companies that produce and sell the initial products with their packaging and communicate their circular ambitions. We also look at reducing the release of microplastics with bio-based coatings.

- **Innovation breakthrough**

These methods allow for closing the loop of material use, especially that of bio-based plastics, to reduce the CO2 footprint. In this way, recycled materials can be reused in ways that will reduce plastic waste and the purposeful reuse of recycled materials. For companies putting plastic packaging on the market, it would be an excellent opportunity to reuse it for marketing purposes.

- **Strategic actions to market**

The PLA grades used for food packaging applications are different from the PLA grades used in textile applications. Adjustments to the material formulations must be made to reach the quality needed to maintain the speed of the industrial processes. A balance of the amount of recycled PLA for food packaging streams must be found through a close collaboration between the textile industry, compounders and recyclers. In the PRESERVE project, it was demonstrated that it is possible to produce multifilaments with recycled PLA coming from food packaging and made non-woven with it. These are the first steps to developing scalable prototypes in the future.

TRL 3-4

TRL 6

R₁ E₁

U₁ S₁ E₁

C₃ Y₄ C₃ L₁ E₁

P₃ E₁ A₁ T₁

2. Sustainability aspects of innovative solutions

How can we ensure the sustainability of innovative solutions? How can we contribute to protecting the Environment and the safety and health of citizens and society?

LCA and eco-design

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is essential in evaluating and guiding the sustainability of innovative bio-based plastics for packaging. It provides a comprehensive framework to assess the environmental impacts of every stage of a product's lifecycle, including raw material extraction, production, distribution, use, and end-of-life. Eco-design complements this approach by focusing on proactively integrating environmental considerations during the design phase, ensuring that packaging solutions are functional and environmentally responsible. Analysing the entire lifecycle makes it possible to identify key areas for improvement, such as reducing greenhouse gas emissions, enhancing material recyclability, or transitioning to renewable resources. This holistic perspective ensures the development of packaging that aligns with both industry needs and sustainability goals.

As part of the PRESERVE project, LCA assessments were carried out on ten benchmark food and non-food packaging demonstrators to compare and evaluate traditional fossil-based products.

Similarly, LCA assessments were carried out on the bio-based products developed by the PRESERVE project, using system boundaries, functional units and assumptions comparable to those used for the benchmark products.

LCA results show a general trend towards higher values for bio-based products than fossil-based ones. These results may seem nonsense, but this trend can also be found in the literature. The bio-based products industry is very young, especially compared to the fossil-based packaging industry. As young as it is, it is an industry with significant variability in processes, materials and development methodologies, and where experimentation is still in full swing.

This, combined with the processes developed by the PRESERVE project, is industrial but still experimental. It results in a high degree of variability and inconsistency, making it difficult to compare with fossil-based products, for which decades of research and experimentation have been conducted.

LCC

The Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analysis will contribute to developing a business plan and drive the market introduction of bio-based packaging in the PRESERVE project by quantifying the economic viability and cost-effectiveness of the newly developed materials.

The direct costs of both the benchmark demonstrators and the products developed by the project were evaluated, considering the costs of both the material and energy inputs involved in the production processes. The environmental costs of the processes studied were also assessed by evaluating the eco-costs. For each impact category analysed in the LCA, this measure expresses a monetary quantification of the process impacts on the different ecosystem compartments and humans. As with the LCA, the results are affected because this is a young industry where many process choices can vary the assessments. There is also a lot of price variability, which follows market trends and international socio-political events. As many of these are feedstocks for which the market still needs to develop fully, unit costs are often high, and the market needs to be fully competitive with equivalent fossil-based materials.

Social LCA

Bio-based packaging can contribute to social well-being by promoting healthier living environments. Reduced pollution and waste can lead to cleaner communities and improved public health. Additionally, using sustainable materials can foster a sense of environmental responsibility and community engagement. The social and socio-economic benefits of implementing new packaging products have been addressed in online surveys. The main conclusions of the survey carried out by PRESERVE can be summarised as follows:

- Although the level of education affects the interest in sustainability and innovative materials, the cost remains the central element considered.
- There is a lot of interest in educational activities, such as thematic workshops and local events, about plastic packaging, its environmental consequences, and the recycling process.
- Consumers could accept a higher final price of the product using sustainable packaging.
- For the industry and actors of the value chain, the main obstacles to applying innovative sustainable materials are difficulties in the production processes, the high cost of the innovative material, and EU and national regulations.

Circularity

The Material Circularity Indicator developed by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation has been used to assess the circularity of the products developed in Preserve. The MCI formula gives credit to the feedstock origin (e.g. biological source, recycled or reused sources), end of life of the products (e.g. recycling, composting...), an extension of the life of the products and insurance that the biological materials remain uncontaminated and biologically accessible.

In this sense, any product manufactured using only virgin feedstock and ending in a landfill at the end of its use phase can be considered an entirely 'linear' product (0). On the other hand, any product that contains no virgin feedstock is ultimately collected for recycling or component reuse. Where the recycling efficiency is 100%, it can be considered a fully 'circular' product (1). In practice, products will sit somewhere between these two extremes, and the MCI measures the level of circularity in the range 0 to 1.

Decision Support System for the selection of materials, pathways and EoL

The Decision Support System (DSS) is a multiparametric, AI-driven tool designed to optimise upcycling and sustainability decisions across the packaging value chain. It serves stakeholders such as packaging designers, recyclers, and end-users by evaluating and selecting sustainable materials, pathways, and end-of-life (EOL) product applications. Integrating data and scenarios from earlier research in the project, the DSS simulates both linear and circular material pathways, considering confidence factors, stakeholder priorities, and life cycle impacts.

In summary, the DSS enabled data-driven decision-making for sustainable innovation in the packaging and materials sector, improving circularity and resource efficiency through an advanced, AI-powered solution.

In PRESERVE it has been demonstrated that the circularity of packaging increases when changing the structure. For instance when moving from a virgin feedstock and non-recyclable packaging with an MCI close to 0, to a bio-based sourced material with a composting end of life, the result for the MCI is near 1. Therefore, this allows to highlight that design is a key step in circularity and that it should be designed for recycling.

STRATEGIC ACTIONS FOR THE FUTURE

The Legislative Framework

The PRESERVE objectives and applications have the potential to contribute to several existing and future EU and national legislations. Continuous monitoring of policy evolution in food and drink packaging was conducted during the PRESERVE project to ensure alignment with emerging legislation. The tables below are part of this monitoring system:

FIELD	LEGISLATION	HIGHLIGHTS	STATUS
PLASTICS	Directive (EU) 2019/904 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment/Single-Use Plastics Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bans throwaway plastic items such as cutlery, plates, straws, beverage stirrers, as well as beverage cups and containers made of EPS, including their covers and lids. • Biodegradable, compostable plastics and bio-based plastics are considered plastic and thus fall under the scope of the SUPD. • Restrictions on so-called 'oxo-degradable' plastics introduced. • Fully enforceable from 2024; revision planned for 2027. 	 In force July 2021
	REACH restriction addressing intentionally added microplastics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The adopted restriction uses a broad definition of microplastics – it covers all synthetic polymer particles below five millimetres that are organic, insoluble and resist degradation. • Prohibits the sale of microplastics as such, and of products to which microplastics have been added on purpose and that release those microplastics when used. 	 In force
	Communication – EU Policy framework on bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides definitions and informs and provides guidance for policy makers. • Priority should be to reduce resource consumption, to keep raw materials in the loop for as long as possible, and to use secondary raw materials instead of primary raw materials. 	 Published Nov. 2022
	Microplastics initiative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aims to close the gaps in scientific knowledge related to the risk and presence of microplastics in the environment, drinking water and food, and related to biodegradability, especially in the marine environment. 	 Ongoing

FIELD	LEGISLATION	HIGHLIGHTS	STATUS
FOOD CONTACT	Commission Regulation (EU) 2022/1616 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Streamlines existing regulations on the development, certification, and use of food contact materials (FCMs). •Covers all existing new recycling technologies since 2008 and future innovative novel plastic recycling technologies under development. 	 In force Sept. 2022
	Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Current specific requirements for the manufacture and marketing of plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food; or already in contact with food; or which can reasonably be expected to come into contact with food. 	 In force
	Revision of EU rules on food contact materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Consultation closed in Jan. 2023. •Adoption planned in 2nd quarter 2023. 	 Ongoing
WASTE	Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Known as Waste Framework Directive. 	 In force
	Proposal for a targeted revision of the Waste framework Directive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Proposing to introduce mandatory and harmonised Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes for textiles in all EU Member States. 	 Published July 2023
PACKAGING & PACKAGING WASTE	Proposal for an EU Regulation on Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Will repeal Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste •Introduces key elements obligations on: sustainability requirements; packaging Design for Recyclability; recyclability standards; design-for-recycling criteria; labelling that indicates whether it is reusable, recyclable, or compostable; recycled content targets; recyclability at scale; innovative packaging; compostable packaging •Will launch a series of secondary legislation on the elements on the previous point. 	 Adopted In corrigendum phase
SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTS	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Revision of EcoDesign Directive. •Aims at building in sustainability throughout the entire product lifecycle, starting at the design phase. •Proposed "Digital Product Passport" plans to contain information on each product's composition, including material and chemical properties, as well as information on their circularity, such as guidance for reuse and repair operators. •Proposal under discussion EP and Council. 	 Under discussion

FIELD	LEGISLATION	HIGHLIGHTS	STATUS
SUSTAINABLE FINANCE	Commission Regulation (EU) 2020/852 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment /Taxonomy Regulation	•Classification system that establishes a list of environmentally sustainable economic activities, providing guidance for companies, investors, and policymakers.	 In force
ENVIRONMENTAL FOOTPRINT	Substantiating claims on environmental performance of products and businesses Initiative	•Upcoming proposal for a regulation •It would propose for companies having to substantiate their environmental claims using EU Product and Organisation Environmental Footprint (PEF / OEF) methods. These methods measure the environmental performance of a product or organisation throughout the value chain, from the extraction of raw materials to the end of life, using 16 environmental impact categories.	 Ongoing
BIOTECHNOLOGY & BIOMANUFACTURING	Communication from the European Commission: Building the future with nature: Boosting Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in the EU	•Proposes a series of targeted actions to boost biotechnology and biomanufacturing in the EU such as leveraging research and boosting innovation, stimulating market demand, streamlining regulatory pathways, elaborating and updating standards, supporting collaboration and synergies, or fostering public and private investments.	 Published March 2024

Policy Recommendations

Strategic actions are necessary to ensure the success of initiatives such as the PRESERVE solutions in biobased packaging because they provide a framework for overcoming barriers, seizing opportunities, and aligning efforts across stakeholders.

Within PRESERVE, we have tried to answer the following questions: Which challenges are we facing in the biobased packaging solutions developed within PRESERVE to reach the market? **What drives innovation?** Which barriers and enablers would companies (brand owners and manufacturers) consider changing to more sustainable packaging?

The answers to these questions, the conclusions and analysis from the results of our project, and the insights from key stakeholders and the PRESERVE Advisory Board have resulted in a list of policy recommendations presented below. We have grouped the policy recommendations into five groups based on their nature. With these policy recommendations, we aim to contribute to the further development of sustainable packaging in Europe and to the legislative framework **presented** in **the previous** section in Tables 1, 2 and 3 of this document.

1. Research, Development and Innovation, Sustainability and Safety

Research also needs investment efforts, and broad or undefined research scopes can dilute efforts, leading to inefficient use of resources and slower progress. Adopting advanced methodologies like life cycle assessment (LCA) and data-driven optimisation techniques can streamline R&D processes. However, there needs to be a unified methodology for assessing the sustainability and safety of biobased packaging. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and other tools should be consistently utilised or applied. The complexity of managing intellectual property (IP) rights, mainly when multiple stakeholders contribute to developing sustainable packaging technologies, can deter collaboration and innovation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Defining focused, actionable research objectives** aligned with market and environmental needs to drive impactful innovation.
- **Enhance Research and Development (R&D):** Expand R&D efforts to include comprehensive LCA, LCC, and SsBD evaluations in innovation. These assessments will ensure that biobased materials achieve environmental, economic, and social sustainability. R&D should focus on developing scalable materials with improved functionality while minimising environmental impacts across their lifecycle..
- **Support innovation in recycling technologies and Infrastructure:** incentives for research and development of advanced sorting technology and recycling methods, particularly for multilayer packaging and biobased materials, enzymatic delamination and material recycling technologies, are critical to improving material recovery. This must go hand in hand with establishing an infrastructure for mixed plastic waste management from post-consumer wastes, able to differentiate towards pure bioplastics or composites.
- **Establishing clear IP-sharing agreements** and adopting open innovation practices can facilitate collaboration while protecting the interests of all parties

2. Scalability, Industrial integration and Value Chain

The biobased packaging industry faces significant challenges in scaling up production. Scalability remains a key obstacle, with limited availability of bio-based raw materials, limited production capacities for biobased packaging materials, and fragmented supply chains. All these factors lead to a high price of raw materials, leaving the final product with a low chance of successfully entering the market due to its high costs. Integrating biobased materials into existing systems without disrupting functionality or needing new investments is critical. The value chain for biobased packaging needs to be more cohesive, with limited collaboration between stakeholders. Transparency among competitors is low, and information sharing remains constrained, slowing the development of practical solutions.

Limited infrastructure for collecting, sorting, and recycling biobased materials reduces their potential to close the loop. Many recycling systems are optimised for fossil-based plastics, creating inefficiencies for biobased packaging.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Scaling Circular Systems:** Invest in increasing recycling and material recovery capacities for biobased materials. EU-led initiatives should focus on supporting industrial-scale systems, including developing tailored sorting and recovery technologies. Scaling production facilities is essential to meet growing demand and close the circularity loop.
- **Strengthen partnerships with suppliers and invest in developing bio-based supply chains** to enhance material availability and reduce costs. Thus, investing in new developments will improve the performance of raw materials, allowing them to be more technically competitive with fossil-based materials.
- **Collaboration with recyclers, packaging manufacturers, and end users** will be essential to integrate the technology into existing systems. All parties must invest in the equipment or adjustments for processing biomaterials. Review the current packaging and define the minimum requirements for each application to adapt the product to real-world needs. This definition will help develop new approaches or alternatives for the market. Partnerships with key market players can help expand production and facilitate the entry of new bio-based solutions into the market.

- **Leveraging pilot programs and incrementing scaling strategies** can mitigate risks and demonstrate feasibility before full-scale deployment, encouraging the industry to invest in these solutions.
- **Build and enhance regional infrastructure** to enable efficient collection, sorting, and recycling of biobased materials. Incorporate LCC analysis in infrastructure planning to ensure cost-effective solutions while achieving environmental goals. Develop recovery systems that align with SsBD principles to minimise risks and optimise resource utilisation.
- **Secure the supply chain of organic raw materials and their quality**, to guarantee constant performance on the production processes and the quality of the packaging.

3. Policy and regulatory hurdles

Navigating a complex and evolving policy framework remains a significant challenge. Over ten strategies, plans, or initiatives and a dozen more laws and regulations with substantial overlaps and inconsistencies exist. Discrepancies between high-level political support, strategies and initiatives for the bioeconomy, the environment, industry and climate and current EU legislation hamper investment and create barriers to market entry and expansion. There are also challenges related to compliance with specific safety requirements, the end-of-waste status of by-products, and food contact applications due to the need for harmonised frameworks.

The absence of harmonised sustainability standards and certifications creates confusion and undermines trust in biobased materials. Additionally, fossil-based plastics benefit from subsidies, creating an uneven playing field that stifles the competitiveness of biobased alternatives. Achieving compliance while supporting the valorisation (commercialisation and utilisation) of new technologies through standardisation is often tricky due to a need for more explicit links between research, policy, and regulatory frameworks. These challenges reflect the intricate relationships between innovation, regulatory compliance, and the development of standards that apply to biobased products throughout their lifecycle.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Ensure participation of relevant experts in intra-department discussions at the European Commission:** involve industry, academia, NGOs, civil society organisations, as well as EU-funded projects developing novel materials, technologies and processes in the preparation of secondary regulation/delegated acts, such as the upcoming deriving from PPWR. EU-funded projects often represent all key stakeholders and possess valuable insights on the sector's development, its potential, the challenges to be overcome and the needs to overcome them. Collaborate with policymakers to create unified frameworks for sustainability assessments, integrating LCA and SsBD methodologies. These standards should ensure comparability and transparency, providing clear guidance for eco-design and circularity in biobased packaging.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Harmonise policy frameworks:** a better-integrated bioeconomy framework with stronger links between the circular economy, environment, climate bioeconomy and industrial strategies is needed as often they are treated as separate concepts when, in fact, the bioeconomy is one-half of the circular economy. Clear, streamlined strategies and unified regulations on using and recycling biobased and biodegradable packaging materials are essential. Regulatory frameworks should ensure these materials meet safety standards without stifling innovation and provide clear guidelines for compliance.
- **Establish solid legislative and regulatory frameworks** that encourage the development of new technologies. An example is the new Regulation 2022/1616 concerning recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food. It opens a window to new recycling technologies that are considered novel, allowing the evolution of recycling techniques that are still at low TRLs in the market. Inconsistencies such as those between the Sustainable Taxonomy Climate Delegated Act and the Delegated Act on Environment and Circular Economy regarding using primary biomass for plastics production must be dissolved. Upcoming delegated acts deriving from the PPWR regulation should avoid stifling innovation.
- **Involve regulatory bodies at an early stage and foster industry and research collaboration:** involving regulators and standards organisations early in the research process can help ensure that new materials are developed with compliance in mind. Collaborative efforts between researchers, industry, and regulators can lead to the co-development of materials that meet technical performance requirements and regulatory standards. Standardisation helps bridge the gap between research and the market, increasing the probability that the market will adopt technological innovations. Horizon-funded EU research projects are melting pots of ideas between research organisations, academia, industry and civil society. EU-funded projects contribute to developing informative or technical aspects such as new materials, processes or specifications, notably to EU-level standardisation efforts.
- **Harmonise standards:** the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN) is critical in developing common frameworks for material safety, biodegradability, and food contact compliance. Harmonised standards would allow companies to meet one set of criteria for multiple markets, reducing the complexity and cost of compliance. The European Commission can steer this process by mandating that CEN develop specific standards.

4. Market competitiveness and cost

The high cost of biobased materials compared to fossil-based options presents a significant barrier to adoption. Insufficient incentives and limited initial investments in raw material production and recycling systems hinder industry growth. A significant barrier to innovation is the substantial capital required to develop new machinery tailored to sustainable packaging concepts that could be solved by using and adapting existing machines for packaging production. Short-term and high Return on Investment (ROI) expectations often inhibit the adoption of sustainable practices. Reducing ROI expectations can make more projects viable, opening the door to incremental yet impactful innovations. Despite the potential environmental benefits of biobased packaging, fossil-based materials remain dominant due to cost-effectiveness, scale of production, supply chain infrastructure, policy and regulatory support and subsidies, and consumer preference and demand. Creating a level playing field for alternative materials is challenging.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Provide financial and policy incentives for biobased packaging:** support the acceleration of adopting eco-friendly alternatives that help create a level playing field. Promote and standardise life cycle assessments for packaging materials, ensuring that environmental impacts are minimised in end-of-life processes and during production and use.
- **Facilitate the development of logistics and management frameworks:** logistics support the process of harvesting underutilised biomass for the manufacturing of biobased products. Life Cycle Assessments can also serve as a tool for identifying sustainability hiccups along the supply and logistics chain. Market readiness also depends on developing infrastructure to handle bioplastics at the end of their lifecycle.
- **Leverage alternative feedstocks:** encourage using 2G and 3G bioplastics and 1G to reduce costs and decrease environmental impacts. Ad hoc marketplaces should be set up to match the offer and demand of 2G and 3G feedstock and plastic mixes and facilitate the supply chain's logistics.

5. Education, awareness and skill development

Transitioning from a linear to a circular economy necessitates new knowledge and skills. Educational programmes must evolve to meet these demands, and corporate training must align with new policies and sustainable practices.

Substantial efforts from policymakers and market players are needed to raise citizen awareness and promote eco-friendly alternatives. End-users often misunderstand terms like “biobased” and “biodegradable,” leading to scepticism about the benefits of biobased packaging. Limited education efforts and inconsistent labelling exacerbate these misconceptions. Consumer scepticism or reluctance to pay more for sustainable packaging can limit market acceptance. Additionally, inconsistent communication about the benefits of bio-based alternatives exacerbates this issue.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Update educational curricula:** align corporate training and academic programs with the new demands of the circular economy, ensuring businesses and workers are equipped for the shift. Offering training programs, fostering academic-industry partnerships, and promoting knowledge exchange can bridge this skills gap.
- **Invest in educational campaigns:** Governments should invest in educational campaigns aimed at consumers and businesses to promote the benefits of sustainable packaging, circular economy practices, and national and EU-level legal commitments. Public understanding and acceptance of biobased and biodegradable packaging and recycling options are crucial for widespread adoption.
- **Public awareness campaigns and harmonised labelling schemes:** labelling products, disposal, and certification schemes will be critical in determining consumers' willingness to pay to combat greenwashing and build public trust in more sustainable practices. The development of labelling schemes that are transparent and credible to customers is key. These schemes must be tied to practical environmental standards, and competent agencies should monitor compliance regularly. Education and public awareness campaigns are key for adequately disposing of bioplastics and biobased materials. Launch campaigns that include easy-to-understand information derived from LCA results, emphasising the environmental advantages of biobased materials. Provide labels and certifications based on SsBD criteria to build consumer trust and empower sustainable purchasing decisions.

Conclusion

As the PRESERVE project concludes, it represents a critical step forward in addressing the environmental challenges posed by packaging materials. Through the development of bio-based, recyclable, and upcyclable packaging solutions, PRESERVE contributes to the transition toward a circular economy and reduced dependency on fossil-based plastics. The project's advancements in eco-design, innovative recycling methodologies, and comprehensive sustainability assessments create a strong foundation for future efforts.

However, the journey toward widespread adoption of sustainable packaging solutions is far from complete. Scalability, cost competitiveness, and regulatory alignment challenges highlight the need for continued innovation and collaboration across industries and policy frameworks. By fostering partnerships and investing in new technologies, stakeholders can build on PRESERVE's achievements to accelerate the transformation of the packaging sector.

The findings and methodologies developed through PRESERVE offer a blueprint for achieving a balance between economic growth, environmental responsibility, and societal benefits. As the lessons of this project are integrated into broader practices, they provide a pathway for a more sustainable future in which packaging plays a vital role in reducing waste and conserving resources.

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